

***Ochthera sauteri* Cresson (Diptera: Ephydriidae), predator of rice whorl maggot (RWM) flies**

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RWM *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino has few recorded natural enemies. Recently, we found an ephydrid fly preying on RWM flies.

The predator *Ochthera sauteri* Cresson (identified by P.J. Clausen, University of Minnesota, USA) is in

the subfamily Parydrinae previously recorded only in Taiwan. The 5- to 7-mm-long adult can be identified by its black and silvery body, 0.16 mm head index value, 3 arisal hairs on the antenna, pointed frons, mantis-like forelegs with 4 long spines, and tibial spur as long as the basal segment of the tarsus, forecoxa and tarsus subequal in length, wings hyaline with tips of vein $R_4 + 5$ and $M_1 + 2$ close to each other (see figure).

The behavior of *O. sauteri* is different from that of its relatives in this mainly phytophagous group. It

walks on the rice foliage or water surface, or dives from the plant to the water to grab sighted prey. The prey is held transversely in its mantis-like forelegs and rapidly pricked by the tibial spur 3-10 times prior to feeding.

The predatory fly laps up the body fluids that ooze from the prey's body. Cage studies showed *Ochthera* live 4-7 d. They prey on species of *Hydrellia*, *Brachydeutera*, *Psilopa*, and *Paralimna*, consuming 4-18 flies/d. They also feed on *Notiphila* spp. at 1-3 flies/d. □

Female of *O. sauteri* (a), frontal view of head (b), side view of face with 3 arisal hairs (c), clypeus (d), mantis-like foreleg stretched to show spur (e) and held at rest (f), hind leg (g), tarsal segments (h-i), and tip of male's abdomen (j). Scale = 1 mm except d, h, and i.